

Calculation of future CH₄ mixing ratios for the ECLIPSE-v6b emission scenarios (version8.0)

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1 Introduction

This document describes a possible approach for the calculation of the CH₄ mixing ratio evolution in the period 2015–2050 for the ECLIPSE-v6b emission data sets¹. The suggested CH₄ mixing ratios are given in Table 7 for the various scenarios. They are a continuation of the historical CMIP6 CH₄ mixing ratios which end in 2014 [Meinshausen et al., 2017].

A first version of the emission data sets became available in 2019 and was used to generate methane concentrations for Earth System Model simulations in the AMAP assessment report. New emission data sets that became available in 2020 were used in simulations with the AMAP climate and air quality emulator (supplementary document) and for the analysis of emissions, radiative forcings, and temperature impacts in Chapters 2 and 7 of the report. Although small differences in the global methane emissions exist between these data sets, the temperature impacts are well within the uncertainty of the ESM simulation results.

More detailed information on the CH₄ emission scenarios can be found in Höglund-Isaksson et al. [2020]. Overall scenario documentation will become available [Klimont et al., in prep.] including a dedicated waste management study [Gómez-Sanabria et al., submitted].

In this document we explain how the CH₄ mixing ratios can be derived, and focus on the reference ECLIPSE-v6b scenario. In Section 2 we describe the box-model approach used to calculate the global CH₄ evolution. In Section 3, we test the box model by performing several sensitivity tests. In Section 4, we try to estimate the best background CH₄ emission strength to be used. In Section 5, we describe the final suggested approach.

2 Description of the box model

In this section we describe the box model used to derive global mean CH₄ mixing ratios.

2.1 Methane lifetime

The evolution of global atmospheric CH₄ can be described by

$$\frac{dB}{dt} = -\frac{1}{\tau_{\text{CH}_4}} B + E, \quad (1)$$

where B is the global atmospheric burden of CH₄ and E the global emission rate of CH₄. The time constant τ_{CH_4} can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{\text{CH}_4}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{OH}}} + \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{strat}}} + \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{soil}}} + \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{trop-Cl}}}. \quad (2)$$

Values of the time constants can be found in the Table 1.

¹ECLIPSE-v6b along with other ECLIPSE emission data sets can be viewed at <https://iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchPrograms/air/Global.emissions.html>.

Table 1: CH₄ lifetime [yr] due to different loss processes for pre-industrial and present-day conditions.

		<i>Pre-industrial</i>	<i>Present-day</i>
Destruction of CH ₄ by tropospheric OH radicals	τ_{OH}	11.76	11.17
Loss in the stratosphere	τ_{strat}	120	id.
Uptake by soils	τ_{soil}	150	id.
Reaction with tropospheric chlorine	$\tau_{\text{trop-Cl}}$	200	id.
Loss to all processes	τ_{CH_4}	9.52	9.13

Table 2: Value of the sensitivity coefficients in Eq. (3).

	$S_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{OH}}$	$S_{\text{NO}_x}^{\text{OH}} (\text{Tg}[\text{N}] \text{yr}^{-1})^{-1}$	$S_{\text{CO}}^{\text{OH}} (\text{Tg}[\text{CO}] \text{yr}^{-1})^{-1}$	$S_{\text{VOC}}^{\text{OH}} (\text{Tg}[\text{VOC}] \text{yr}^{-1})^{-1}$	$S_T^{\tau_{\text{CH}_4}} \text{K}^{-1}$
IPCC [2001]	-0.32	0.0042	-0.000105	-0.000315	0.0316
Stocker et al. [2013]	-0.31				

2.2 Impacts on lifetime

Table 1 gives estimates for the lifetime of CH₄ under pre-industrial and present-day conditions [Prather et al., 2012; Voulgarakis et al., 2013]. To calculate the lifetime for other conditions, we use the following approach. The lifetime (τ_{OH}) due to loss by reaction with OH can be described as (see IPCC [2001, Table 4.11])

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{\text{OH}}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{OH}}^0} \left(\left(\frac{B_{\text{CH}_4}}{B_{\text{CH}_4}^0} \right)^{S_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{OH}}} \times \exp \left(S_{\text{NO}_x}^{\text{OH}} \Delta E_{\text{NO}_x} + S_{\text{CO}}^{\text{OH}} \Delta E_{\text{CO}} + S_{\text{VOC}}^{\text{OH}} \Delta E_{\text{VOC}} \right) + S_T^{\tau_{\text{CH}_4}} \Delta T \right). \quad (3)$$

The first part of Eq. (3) expresses the impact of the CH₄ burden and the NO_x, CO, and VOC emissions on the tropospheric CH₄ loss rate. The second part ($S_T^{\tau_{\text{CH}_4}} \Delta T$) expresses the impact of changing atmospheric temperatures on the tropospheric CH₄ loss rate. The values of the sensitivity coefficients are given in Table 2. Notice that the units of the coefficient $S_{\text{NO}_x}^{\text{OH}}$ are $(\text{Tg}[\text{N}] \text{yr}^{-1})^{-1}$, so NO_x emission changes (ΔE_{NO_x}) should be given in $\text{Tg}[\text{N}] \text{yr}^{-1}$. The values in Table 2 on the first row are the values from IPCC [2001]. An updated value from Stocker et al. [2013] for $S_{\text{CH}_4}^{\text{OH}}$ is shown on the second row.

In the box-model calculation, we have applied the values from IPCC [2001], but with the updated value from Stocker et al. [2013].

2.3 Emissions

CH₄ emissions Table 3 contains global total CH₄ emission estimates for ECLIPSE-v6b [Höglund-Isaksson et al., 2020]. These CH₄ emissions are also shown in the upper left panel of Fig. 1.

To calculate the evolution of the global CH₄ mixing ratio, one needs the time evolution of the total CH₄ emissions (anthropogenic + natural emissions). However, ECLIPSE-v6b only contains part of what is referred here as natural emissions, i.e., open burning of agricultural waste. Natural CH₄ emissions are very uncertain, and assumed to vary between 100 and 300 Tg yr⁻¹. Prather et al. [2012] estimated the natural CH₄ emissions as 202 Tg yr⁻¹.

The two scenarios ECLIPSE-v6b and ECLIPSE-v6b-nat (in Table 3 and Fig. 1) differ in the amount of natural emissions included in the data set: ECLIPSE-v6b-nat is as ECLIPSE-v6b, but contains additional contributions from forest fires, savannah and soil emissions (however still not all natural contributions). As none of these two data sets contains the total natural contribution, both will therefore need an additional natural background CH₄ emission amount.

From now on, we only use the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat data set : for that set we will use an additional CH₄ background natural emission strength of 230 Tg yr⁻¹ (see Sections 3.1 and 4).

Table 3: Global CH₄ emission totals [Tgyr⁻¹] in the ECLIPSE-v6b data set. The ECLIPSE-v6b-nat contains additional natural sources : forest fires, savannah, and soil emissions.

	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
ECLIPSE-v6b													
CH ₄	302.5	287.4	290.7	315.3	321.3	337.3	349.3	367.5	380.9	396.9	415.5	429.9	444.7
NO _x	112.6	117.4	117.9	124.4	128.3	127.0	121.1	116.5	113.4	114.2	115.0	116.8	118.6
CO	549.9	565.8	537.9	542.6	528.8	548.9	508.5	485.0	464.5	456.3	448.2	447.9	447.7
VOC	115.4	116.5	109.4	109.0	108.6	112.0	111.0	110.3	108.7	108.9	109.2	110.4	111.6
ECLIPSE-v6b-nat													
CH ₄	312.0	296.9	300.2	328.1	334.3	350.3	362.4	380.7	394.2	410.3	428.9	443.4	458.3
NO _x	127.9	132.8	133.5	140.3	143.7	141.8	136.2	132.0	129.4	130.4	131.3	133.2	135.0
CO	914.9	930.8	902.9	907.7	862.4	849.0	802.3	773.9	748.6	734.8	721.0	714.8	708.6
VOC	182.9	184.0	176.9	176.4	169.8	169.6	167.3	165.4	162.7	161.8	160.8	160.7	160.6

Table 4: CH₄ mixing ratios [ppb] from CMIP6 between year 2005 and 2014 are shown in the first row. The last two rows show values from Stocker et al. [2013] and AGAGE.

Year	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CMIP6	1783.36	1783.42	1788.95	1798.42	1802.10	1807.85	1813.07	1815.26	1822.58	1831.47
IPCC[2013]	1774						1803			
AGAGE	1773.89	1774.19	1780.69	1788.88	1792.37	1796.57	1803.04	1809.3		

NO_x/CO/VOC emissions To express the CH₄ lifetime, one also needs the (change in) emissions of NO_x, CO, and VOCs. The global emission amounts for NO_x, CO, and VOCs in ECLIPSE-v6b and ECLIPSE-v6b-nat are also given in Table 3 and shown in Fig. 1. Also for NO_x, CO, and VOCs, the ECLIPSE-v6b and ECLIPSE-v6b-nat data sets do not contain all natural emission contributions. However, one is only supposed to know the change in NO_x, CO, and VOC emissions w.r.t. a reference period. This reference period will be chosen to be the year 2005 (see Section 3.1).

For none of the emissions a seasonal cycle has been taken into account.

2.4 Initial conditions for CH₄ mixing ratio

To solve the differential equation in Eq. (1), one needs initial conditions for the CH₄ burden B . A possibility might be to choose one of the years between 1990 and 2014, and take the corresponding CH₄ mixing ratio from CMIP6 [Meinshausen et al., 2017]. In the Table 4 are given the CH₄ mixing ratios [ppb] for the years 1990 until 2014 from CMIP6.

The CH₄ historical CMIP6 mixing ratios are considerably higher than the CMIP5 mixing ratios [Meinshausen et al., 2017].

2.5 Conversion factor

Whereas emissions are given in units of Tg yr⁻¹ and burdens expressed in units of Tg, the initial conditions are given in units of mixing ratio. The method is sensitive for the conversion factor used to convert atmospheric CH₄ mixing ratios [mol mol⁻¹] into atmospheric burdens [Tg]. We have used a conversion factor of 2.78 Tg ppb⁻¹ [Solomon et al., 2007, Table 7.6].

2.6 Reference value and time for τ_{OH}^0

We have assumed that the present-day reference value for τ_{OH}^0 (11.17 days, see Table 1) was valid for the year 2005, when the atmospheric CH₄ mixing ratio was 1783.36 ppb [Meinshausen et al., 2017]. The emission changes ΔE_{NO_x} ,

Figure 1: Overview of the emission amounts of CH_4 , NO_x , CO , and VOCs [Tg yr^{-1}] for the ECLIPSE-v6b and ECLIPSE-v6b-nat data set. These emission estimates differ in the amount of natural emissions included. Emission data is available for 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, 2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, and 2050, and has been interpolated linearly for the other years.

Figure 2: Global mean CH_4 mixing ratio using scenario ECLIPSE-v6b-nat (blue line), starting on 1st Jan 2015.

ΔE_{CO} and ΔE_{VOC} are therefore also taken with respect to the emissions of the year 2005.

3 Box model integrations using ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions

Here we present a few integrations of the box model. The first case is some kind of a reference case.

3.1 Reference

Setup The setup of the integration is :

Initial conditions : CH_4 mixing ratio on Jan 1st 2015 from CMIP6 : 1835 ppb. This values is obtained by extrapolating the annual mean values for 2013 and 2014 of Meinshausen et al. [2017] to Jan 1st 2015.

Impact of $\text{NO}_x/\text{CO}/\text{VOC}$: all three taken into account.

Impact of ΔT : not taken into account.

Emission scenario : ECLIPSE-v6b-nat.

Additional background natural CH_4 emission : 230 Tg yr^{-1} .

Results The calculated CH_4 mixing ratios are shown in Fig. 2.

Discussion The new scenario (from 2015 onwards) seems to line up well with the historical CMIP6 mixing ratio (which ends in 2014).

3.2 Sensitivity to $\text{NO}_x/\text{CO}/\text{VOC}$ emissions

Aim We try to investigate how strongly the CH_4 mixing ratios depend on including the impact of NO_x , CO and VOC emissions.

Setup As in the reference case. We distinguish among the following approaches :

v6b-nat- $\text{NO}_x\text{-CO-VOC}$: all three ($\text{NO}_x/\text{CO}/\text{VOC}$) impacts are taken into account

v6b-nat- NO_x : only the NO_x impact is taken into account

v6b-nat- CO : only the CO impact is taken into account

v6b-nat- VOC : only the VOC impact is taken into account

v6b-nat : none of the three impacts is taken into account

Results The results of these sensitivity tests are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Global mean CH_4 mixing ratios using scenario ECLIPSE-v6b-nat, starting on Jan 1st 2015. The different lines differ in whether the impact of NO_x , CO, or VOC emissions is taken into account.

Discussion

- Increasing NO_x emissions lead to a shorter lifetime of CH_4 and lower CH_4 mixing ratios. As the NO_x emissions decrease after 2015 (see upper right panel in Fig. 1), including the effect of NO_x will lengthen the CH_4 lifetime and increase the CH_4 burden.
- Increasing CO emissions lead to a longer CH_4 lifetime and higher CH_4 mixing ratios. As the CO emissions decrease after 2015 (see lower left panel in Fig. 1), including the effect of CO will shorten the CH_4 lifetime and lower the CH_4 burden.
- Increasing VOC emissions have in principle the effect of leading to a longer CH_4 lifetime and higher CH_4 concentrations. As the VOC emissions decrease after 2015 (see lower right panel in Fig. 1), including the effect of VOC will shorten the CH_4 lifetime and lower the CH_4 burden.
- The combination of including all three impacts ($\text{NO}_x/\text{CO}/\text{VOC}$) leads to a slightly shorter CH_4 lifetime and lower CH_4 mixing ratios.

3.3 Sensitivity to start year

Aim Here we investigate whether one can reproduce the CMIP6 CH_4 mixing ratios [Meinshausen et al., 2017] when starting the box-model integration at Jan 1st 1990, and using ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions from 1990 onwards. If this agreement would be reasonable, this would give confidence in the box model and the assumed additional CH_4 background emission amount of 230 Tg yr^{-1} .

Setup The setup is as in the reference case, except that we start the integration in 1990 and use the 1989/1990 CH_4 mixing ratio from CMIP6 as initial conditions : the initial mixing ratio on Jan 1st 1990 is taken as 1711.52 ppb.

Results The result of the integration starting in 1990 is shown in Fig. 4.

Discussion The behaviour of CH_4 mixing ratio is not well reproduced over the 1990–2014 period.

3.4 Sensitivity to temperature increase

Aim We try to investigate how strongly the CH_4 mixing ratios depend on including the impact of temperature changes on the lifetime of CH_4 (see the term $S_T^{\text{CH}_4} \Delta T$ in Eq. (3)).

Figure 4: Global mean CH_4 mixing ratio using scenario ECLIPSE-v6b-nat, starting on Jan 1st 1990.

Figure 5: Global mean CH_4 mixing ratios using scenario ECLIPSE-v6b-nat, starting on Jan 1st 2015. The different lines differ in the assumed temperature increase over the period 2005–2050.

Setup We assume 4 different temperature scenarios for the period 2005–2050. Temperature changes will have an impact on the lifetime of CH_4 via the coefficient $S_T^{\text{CH}_4} = 0.0316 \text{ K}^{-1}$ (see Table 2). The 4 different temperature evolutions we investigate :

- v6b-nat-NOx-CO-VOC : no temperature change. This case is identical to the reference case from Section 3.1.
- v6b-nat-NOx-CO-VOC+1K : temperature increases linearly by 1 K over the period 2005–2050.
- v6b-nat-NOx-CO-VOC+2K : temperature increases linearly by 2 K over the period 2005–2050.
- v6b-nat-NOx-CO-VOC+3K : temperature increases linearly by 3 K over the period 2005–2050.

Results The results of these sensitivity tests are shown in Fig. 5.

Discussion

- Increasing temperatures shorten considerably the lifetime of CH_4 , and lead to lower CH_4 mixing ratios. Taking into account the observed temperature change in the period 1990–2015 might also improve the integration over that period (see Section 3.3).

Figure 6: Global emission rates for CH_4 , NO_x , CO , and VOC from anthropogenic surface activities (red), biomass burning (black), and aviation (blue) over the 1750–2014 period in the CMIP6 data set.

Figure 7: Global CH_4 mixing ratio derived from CMIP6 emissions.

3.5 Sensitivity to emission data set : using CMIP6 emissions over the period 1850–2014

Here we investigate whether we can reproduce the observed CH_4 mixing ratios when we use the CMIP6 emissions of CH_4 , NO_x , CO , and VOC . Figure 6 shows timeseries of the CMIP6 global emission rates for the period 1750–2014 for anthropogenic surface emissions, biomass burning emissions, and emissions from aviation. Table 5 shows the total CMIP6 emissions for the 1990–2014 period. For comparison, the table also shows the emissions of ECLIPSE-v6b-nat over the same period (taken from Table 3).

Figure 7 shows the CH_4 mixing ratio one obtains when using the box model with the CMIP6 emissions. We have done two different integrations : (i) in the first one we have not taken into account the global temperature change over the 1850–2014 period; (ii) in the second integration, we have taken into account the temperature change over the historical period, using the HadCRUT4 data set. In these two integrations, we used an additional constant CH_4 background emission amount of $250 \text{ Tg}[\text{CH}_4]\text{yr}^{-1}$. With this choice of supplementary emissions, we reasonably well reproduce the observed CH_4 mixing ratio from 1850 to 1990. However, we do not reproduce well the CH_4 mixing ratio over the period 1990–2014.

Table 5: Global emission rates [Tgyr⁻¹] of CH₄, NO_x, CO, and VOC in CMIP6. The values for ECLIPSE-v6b-nat are shown for comparison.

Year	CH ₄	NO _x	CO	VOC	CH ₄	NO _x	CO	VOC
	CMIP6				ECLIPSE-v6b-nat			
1990	305.4	125.7	940.6	203.1	312.0	127.9	914.9	182.9
1991	318.8	130.4	1130.3	244.5				
1992	299.5	127.2	913.4	198.3				
1993	299.6	130.5	941.9	203.9				
1994	310.4	132.3	1060.5	231.1				
1995	305.6	132.9	955.0	206.5	296.9	132.8	930.8	184.0
1996	307.5	132.8	930.1	200.9				
1997	331.6	137.6	1205.8	264.9				
1998	315.5	139.1	1084.5	232.2				
1999	309.7	134.5	941.0	205.2				
2000	310.5	135.6	888.0	195.6	300.2	133.5	902.9	176.9
2001	313.2	135.9	881.5	196.2				
2002	322.6	137.7	970.7	218.5				
2003	328.4	140.2	944.3	214.4				
2004	339.2	146.4	945.6	216.8				
2005	346.7	149.8	950.9	218.9	328.1	140.3	907.7	176.4
2006	356.7	153.2	985.3	229.8				
2007	355.4	158.2	946.5	219.9				
2008	360.9	157.8	913.1	214.9				
2009	364.6	152.8	918.6	219.0				
2010	371.2	155.5	953.3	224.7	334.3	143.7	862.4	169.8
2011	373.0	159.4	907.3	218.9				
2012	381.2	158.4	950.0	229.3				
2013	382.0	156.2	902.0	219.6				
2014	388.3	155.7	964.7	233.7				
2015					350.3	141.8	849.0	169.6

4 Estimating the time-varying CH₄ background emission in the past

4.1 Motivation

We encounter considerable difficulties in reproducing the observed CH₄ mixing ratios over the period 1990–2014, both when using the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat as when using the CMIP6 emission data. In Section 3.3, we saw that using the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat data set plus a constant background CH₄ emission of 230 Tg yr⁻¹ and starting the box-model integration in 1990, leads to a considerable underestimation of the CH₄ mixing ratio over the 1990–2014 period, and to a too strong rate of change in the mixing ratio. In Section 3.5 we saw that using the CMIP6 emission data set plus a constant background CH₄ emission of 250 Tg yr⁻¹, we overestimate the mixing ratio in the 1990–2014 period, and similarly to the case above, we also overestimate the rate of change in that period.

Over the period 1990–2014, the CMIP6 approach and ECLIPSE-v6b-nat obtained concentrations differ considerably. This is mainly caused by the different chosen background CH₄ emission of 230 Tg yr⁻¹ for ECLIPSE-v6b-nat and 250 Tg yr⁻¹ for CMIP6. We assume that lowering in the CMIP6 integration the natural background emissions from 1990 onwards, would give CH₄ concentrations reasonably similar to the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat, but still an overestimated rate of change.

Many reasons might contribute to the deficiencies seen in the box-model integrations, and possible causes are :

- (i) the concept of the box model might be too simple in general (Eqs. (2) and (3));
- (ii) the sensitivity coefficients in Eq. (3) might be inaccurate;
- (iii) the emission amounts might be wrong, as well for CH₄ as for NO_x, CO and VOC.

To obtain a better correspondence between the CH₄ mixing ratios obtained with the box model and the observed CH₄ concentrations given by Meinshausen et al. [2017], one could try to change the value of the sensitivity coefficients, or try to modify the evolution over time of the emissions. To limit the complexity of this approach (and to limit the degrees of freedom), we will assume here that the largest uncertainty is in the additional CH₄ background emissions, and therefore propose to allow for a time-varying background emission amount of CH₄. The values we obtain over the 1990–2014 period might then be the basis for the natural background emission amount to be used for the 2015–2050 period : one could, e.g., assume that the mean value found over the 2005–2014 period can also be used in the future (2015–2050).

4.2 Deriving time-varying natural emissions

Here we try to find the natural emission amounts that allow us to best reproduce the observed CH₄ mixing ratio. We do it first for the 1850–2014 period using the CMIP6 emissions, and then for the 1990–2014 period using the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions. We will also test the sensitivity to taking into account the impact of NO_x, CO and VOCs emissions, and to taking into account the temperature change over the historical period (HadCRUT4).

Using CMIP6 emissions We start the integration in 1850, and estimate the background emissions such that observed CH₄ mixing ratios can be reproduced. Figure 8 shows the derived timeseries of background CH₄ emissions. The derived natural background contribution is reasonably constant over the 1850–1990 period (around 250 Tg yr⁻¹), but decreases over the 1990–2014 period (down to around 200 Tg yr⁻¹ in 2010). One can also see that taking into account the impact of NO_x/CO/VOCs, leads to lower CH₄ background emission estimates. The corresponding assumed longer lifetime is probably caused by the impact of CO and VOCs emission increases prevailing over the NO_x emission increases.

Using ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions We start the integration on 1st Jan 1990, use ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions, and estimate the background emissions such that observed CH₄ mixing ratios can be reproduced over the period 1990–2014. Figure 9 shows the derived timeseries of background CH₄ emissions. The evolution over this 25-year period of the derived CH₄ background emissions is rather similar to the values derived when using the CMIP6 emission, but shows a slightly weaker downward trend. Table 6 shows the actual derived emission values. The averaged background emission strength over the 2005–2014 period is 230 Tg yr⁻¹, and that value will be used as a constant background emission in the box model when using it for the 2015–2050 period.

5 Evolution of CH₄ mixing ratio : suggested approach

To calculate the suggested CH₄ mixing ratio for the 2015–2050 period, we have taken the following approach :

1. to start at 1st Jan 2015 with a CH₄ mixing ratio of 1835 ppb,

Figure 8: Derived background CH₄ emissions such that observed CH₄ mixing ratios are reproduced. The emissions used are from CMIP6.

Figure 9: Derived background CH₄ emissions such that observed CH₄ mixing ratios are reproduced for the period 1990–2014. The emissions used are from ECLIPSE-v6b-nat.

Table 6: Additional CH₄ background emissions needed to reproduce the observed CH₄ mixing ratios over the 1990–2014 period when using the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions data. The average emission over the period 2005–2014 is 230 Tg yr⁻¹.

Year	CH ₄ emissions [Tg yr ⁻¹]
1990	237.2
1991	242.0
1992	236.2
1993	232.3
1994	241.8
1995	241.4
1996	240.4
1997	250.2
1998	256.7
1999	248.5
2000	234.8
2001	232.9
2002	237.2
2003	231.9
2004	218.4
2005	213.8
2006	222.2
2007	236.2
2008	236.1
2009	231.8
2010	234.4
2011	227.5
2012	228.2
2013	236.2
2014	235.3

Figure 10: Global CH_4 mixing ratios for the ECLIPSE-v6b scenario, using the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions and a constant background CH_4 emission of 230 Tg yr^{-1} . The temperature evolution taken into account differs among the experiments: 'hadcrutsmooth' implies that the historical temperature change is taken into account over the period 2015–2018, and '0.xKpD' refers to the temperature change in Kelvin per decade taken into account from 2018 onwards. Integrations started at 1st Jan 2015.

2. to include the impact of NO_x , CO, VOC emissions on the lifetime of CH_4 ,
3. to use the ECLIPSE-v6b-nat emissions time series (as they contain already a larger part of natural emissions),
4. to use a constant CH_4 natural background emission of 230 Tg yr^{-1} (the averaged value of the derived estimates for the period 2005–2014 in Table 6), and
5. to use the HadCRUT4 temperature data up to 2018 and to assume a temperature increase of $0.2 \text{ K decade}^{-1}$ after 2018.

Figure 10 shows timeseries of the CH_4 mixing ratio over the 2015–2050 period (showing some additional temperature sensitivity integrations). The timeseries of the CH_4 mixing ratios following the standard setup for various scenarios are given in Table 7.

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Table 7: Methane mixing ratios [ppb] derived for various ECLIPSE-v6b scenarios, assuming a CH₄ background emission strength of 230 Tg yr⁻¹. The temperature evolution taken into account is HadCRUT4 until 2018, and a 0.2 K decade⁻¹ increase from 2019 onwards up to 2050. The indications (2019) and (2020) refer to when the data sets became available.

Year	v6b (2019)	v6b MFR (2019)	v6b BASE-CLE (2020)	v6b BASE-MFR (2020)	v6b BASE-NFC (2020)	v6b BASE-SLCF (2020)	v6b CPS-NFC (2020)	v6b SDS-MFR (2020)
2015	1837.94	1837.94	1837.94	1837.94	1837.95	1837.94	1837.94	1837.94
2016	1844.64	1844.64	1844.70	1844.70	1844.59	1844.70	1844.64	1844.67
2017	1851.61	1851.61	1851.83	1851.83	1851.40	1851.83	1851.62	1851.73
2018	1858.89	1858.89	1859.37	1859.37	1858.42	1859.37	1858.91	1859.13
2019	1866.41	1866.41	1867.25	1867.25	1865.60	1867.25	1866.45	1866.84
2020	1874.14	1873.93	1875.41	1875.19	1872.90	1875.16	1874.19	1874.56
2021	1882.28	1877.82	1884.01	1879.47	1880.50	1878.87	1882.26	1878.37
2022	1891.00	1875.26	1893.18	1877.15	1888.52	1875.06	1890.77	1875.20
2023	1900.25	1866.66	1902.88	1868.67	1896.95	1864.20	1899.69	1865.48
2024	1910.00	1852.49	1913.07	1854.49	1905.75	1846.86	1908.97	1849.74
2025	1920.19	1833.35	1923.70	1835.25	1914.88	1823.76	1918.59	1828.61
2026	1930.59	1812.81	1934.53	1814.56	1924.12	1799.02	1928.40	1805.78
2027	1941.00	1793.70	1945.37	1795.31	1933.30	1775.90	1938.29	1784.17
2028	1951.41	1776.00	1956.20	1777.49	1942.42	1754.37	1948.25	1763.80
2029	1961.82	1759.61	1967.04	1760.98	1951.49	1734.32	1958.27	1744.56
2030	1972.24	1744.42	1977.88	1745.68	1960.51	1715.64	1968.34	1726.37
2031	1982.71	1730.25	1988.80	1731.41	1969.57	1698.43	1978.59	1709.44
2032	1993.27	1716.94	1999.89	1718.01	1978.73	1682.74	1989.12	1693.87
2033	2003.90	1704.43	2011.13	1705.41	1987.99	1668.48	1999.91	1679.57
2034	2014.61	1692.65	2022.50	1693.55	1997.33	1655.51	2010.92	1666.44
2035	2025.40	1681.54	2033.99	1682.37	2006.75	1643.71	2022.15	1654.36
2036	2036.34	1671.06	2045.60	1671.83	2016.29	1632.43	2033.62	1642.71
2037	2047.49	1661.16	2057.31	1661.86	2025.97	1621.15	2045.36	1631.00
2038	2058.85	1651.78	2069.11	1652.43	2035.79	1609.86	2057.36	1619.22
2039	2070.39	1642.90	2081.00	1643.49	2045.73	1598.57	2069.57	1607.38
2040	2082.10	1634.47	2092.97	1635.01	2055.77	1587.29	2081.99	1595.51
2041	2093.80	1626.46	2104.90	1626.96	2065.86	1576.29	2094.48	1583.88
2042	2105.38	1618.85	2116.71	1619.31	2075.94	1565.78	2106.96	1572.73
2043	2116.83	1611.61	2128.41	1612.03	2086.01	1555.72	2119.43	1562.03
2044	2128.17	1604.71	2140.00	1605.10	2096.08	1546.08	2131.88	1551.74
2045	2139.40	1598.13	2151.50	1598.49	2106.13	1536.84	2144.31	1541.84
2046	2150.54	1591.84	2162.91	1592.16	2116.13	1528.06	2156.67	1532.47
2047	2161.61	1585.81	2174.23	1586.11	2126.06	1519.79	2168.94	1523.72
2048	2172.61	1580.03	2185.47	1580.30	2135.90	1512.00	2181.12	1515.55
2049	2183.55	1574.47	2196.63	1574.73	2145.67	1504.64	2193.22	1507.91
2050	2194.43	1569.13	2207.73	1569.36	2155.38	1497.68	2205.23	1500.76

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